

CLINICAL APPROACH AND WOUND MANAGEMENT IN THE TREATMENT OF DIABETIC FOOT ULCERS

Senem Güneş Kara^{1*}

Keywords

Diabetic foot ulcers,
Debridement,
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ABSTRACT

The most common reasons for hospital admissions among diabetic patients include monitoring of blood sugar regulation, diabetic ketoacidosis, renal failure, retinopathies, and foot problems. Surgical debridement, considered the primary treatment for diabetic foot ulcers, is performed to reduce pressure caused by weight-bearing on the ulcer, and to address lower extremity ischemia and foot infections. The care and management of diabetic foot ulcers, which pose a serious health problem and are significant causes of morbidity and mortality both globally and in our country, are of utmost importance. A multidisciplinary approach is essential for managing diabetic foot ulcers. Within this multidisciplinary team, nurses play a life-saving role as they are actively involved in the patient's treatment and care process and spend the most time with the patient. This case study was planned to present the clinical approach and wound management in the care of a patient with a diabetic foot ulcer located under the right big toe. Diabetic foot ulcers are a global concern due to their significant contribution to amputation rates. Managing chronic wounds is an extremely challenging and complex process. A multidisciplinary team approach is essential for the care and management of diabetic foot ulcers. Effective wound management requires identifying the underlying cause, implementing cause-specific treatment and care, considering other risk factors, and applying individualized treatment and care tailored to each patient. For this reason, in managing diabetic foot ulcers, nurses play a pivotal role from the initial patient encounter. This includes taking a comprehensive medical history, identifying the patient-specific risk factors, conducting physical examinations to assess the affected foot for temperature, moisture, color, edema, and capillary refill time, performing neurovascular assessments, monitoring circulation through pulse evaluation, examining the skin surrounding the ulcer, and planning, implementing, and evaluating interventions to identify pathogens causing the ulcer. These steps are the cornerstone of care.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes Mellitus (DM) is a group of metabolic disorders characterized by abnormalities in carbohydrate, protein, and fat metabolism due to a deficiency or absence of insulin secreted by the pancreas or partial or complete ineffectiveness of the insulin hormone. This condition requires continuous medical care and treatment. Diabetes can be categorized into type 1 and type 2. Type 1 diabetes is characterized by hyperglycemia resulting from autoimmune attacks and damage to pancreatic β -cells, whereas type 2 diabetes is primarily associated with obesity, reduced insulin production by the pancreas, and insulin resistance caused by β -cell dysfunction, making it a chronic metabolic disease^{1,2,3,4}. The prevalence of diabetes continues to increase significantly worldwide^{5,6}. In 2021, it was reported that there were 536.6 million people with diabetes, and this number is expected to rise to 783.2 million globally by 2045⁷.

The most common reasons for hospital admissions among diabetic patients include monitoring blood sugar regulation, diabetic ketoacidosis, renal failure, retinopathies, and foot problems. In addition to the blood sugar and insulin irregularities caused by DM itself, long-term complications such as peripheral neuropathy and peripheral vascular disease—resulting in peripheral organ and extremity involvement—are significant causes of morbidity and mortality. These complications increase patients' dependency on others and reduce their quality of life. Reports indicate that approximately 19–34% of diabetic patients develop complications with diabetic foot ulcers, and 20–30% of these cases result in limb amputation^{8,9}.

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Surgical debridement, defined as the first-line treatment for diabetic foot ulcers, is performed to reduce the pressure caused by weight-bearing on the ulcer and to treat lower extremity ischemia and foot infections. Randomized clinical trials support therapies aimed at accelerating wound healing and culture-based oral antibiotics for localized osteomyelitis. Multidisciplinary care, typically involving podiatrists, infectious disease specialists, and vascular surgeons in close collaboration with primary care clinicians, has been associated with lower major amputation rates compared to standard care (3.2% vs. 4.4%; odds ratio, 0.40; 95% CI, 0.32–0.51). Approximately 30–40% of diabetic foot ulcers heal within 12 weeks, and recurrence rates are estimated to be 42% within 1 year and 65% within 5 years¹⁰.

The care and management of diabetic foot ulcers, which are serious health problems and significant causes of mortality and morbidity both in our country and globally, are critically important. Accordingly, this case study was designed to present the clinical approach and wound management of a patient with a diabetic foot ulcer located under the right big toe.

CASE

Our patient is a 52-year-old male with an 18-year history of diabetes mellitus. He has been using insulin (Apidra 3x10 units, Lantus 1x30 units). The patient has a history of bypass surgery one year ago and comorbidities including hypertension and hyperlipidemia. His routine medications include Novartis 50 mg/100 mg 1x1, Jardiance 10 mg 2x1, Ator 40 mg 1x1, Agrilor 90 mg 2x1, Corelan 5 mg 1x1, Ecopirin 100 mg 1x1, Problok 50 mg 1x1, and Coversyl 10 mg 1x1.

The patient presented to our wound care outpatient clinic on March 5, 2024, with a wound history that began approximately one and a half months earlier as swelling on the right big toe. Routine laboratory tests, foot X-rays, and arterial/venous Doppler ultrasound examinations for both the right and left feet were requested.

The laboratory results for March 5, 2024, are as follows:

HbA1C: 9.54%	FBG: 169 mg/ dl	Urea: 27,2mg/ dl	Hb: 9,7g/ dl	Hct: 3 2.5%	CRP: 3,89 mg/L
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Bilateral Lower Extremity Arterial RDUS Findings: In the bilateral common iliac, common femoral, superficial and deep femoral arteries, popliteal artery, and segments of the crural arteries, as well as the tibialis anterior, posterior, and left

dorsalis pedis arteries, patent flow and a triphasic flow pattern were observed. The vessel lumens were open, with no significant plaque formation noted. No hemodynamically significant stenosis was observed, except for a 20–50% stenosis in the right dorsalis pedis artery.

Bilateral lower extremity venous RDUS findings: In the bilateral common femoral, superficial and deep femoral, and popliteal veins, the patent flow was noted with open vessel lumens. Compression and augmentation responses were intact. No spontaneous or Valsalva-induced venous reflux was observed. The flow in the great and small saphenous veins was patent, with no reflux detected during the Valsalva maneuver.

Conclusion: Bilateral lower extremity venous RDUS findings were within normal limits.

Based on the routine examinations, wound care and debridement were decided upon. The patient was followed up weekly with daily dressing changes. However, as local wound care and debridement were insufficient, surgical debridement was planned for the necrotic tissue wound under the right big toe. The patient was scheduled for admission to the wound care clinic on March 19, 2024, for surgical debridement. Laboratory tests were updated, and consultations were requested for the planned admission. The patient's test results and evaluations are presented in Table 1.

On March 19, 2024, the patient was admitted to our clinic for surgical debridement. Preoperative preparations included routine laboratory tests, a chest X-ray, and an electrocardiogram (ECG), which completed the anesthesia evaluation.

The anesthesia team assessed that the surgery was appropriate with an ASA II status, provided Agrilor was discontinued 5 days prior to the operation. Additionally, the patient, who has a history of bypass surgery, was evaluated by a cardiologist. The cardiology recommendation included discontinuing Agrilor, continuing Ecopirin, and proceeding with the surgery at low risk. The patient's clinical orders are summarized in Table 2.

The patient underwent surgical debridement on March 21, 2024. On March 25, based on CRP and culture results, the patient was reconsulted with an infectious disease specialist. It was recommended that the patient complete the Cezolon treatment for 10 days and that Augmentin (3 × 1 g) and Ciprofloxacin (2 × 500 mg) be prescribed upon discharge.

Additionally, the patient, who reported itching, was referred to a dermatology consultation. Due to the region being an earthquake-affected area, scabies, which is commonly seen in

Figure 1. Initial Presentation to the Clinic on March 5, 2024

Figure 2. Post-surgical debridement on March 21, 2024.

Figure 3. Dressing with W CURA D on March 24, 2024.

Figure 4. Dressing with Aquacell on April 4, 2024.

Figure 5. Dressing with Aquacell on April 29, 2024.

Figure 6. Dressing with Aquacell on May 18, 2024.

Figure 7. Dressing with Aquacell on June 3, 2024.

Figure 8. Dressing with Fito cream on October 8, 2024.

Table 1. Tests and Evaluations

Patient clinical evaluation			
19 March 2024	Crp: 2.21	Procalcitonin: 0,05	Wound culture: Enterococcus faecalis growth.
25 March 2024	Crp: 2,5	Procalcitonin: 0,04	Wound culture: Enterococcus faecalis growth.
5 April 2024	Crp: 6,5	Procalcitonin: 0,04	Wound culture: Contaminated with skin flora.
Internal Medicine Consultation Note: For the patient hospitalized with a diagnosis of diabetic foot for debridement purposes, it was recommended to increase Apidra to 314 units and Lantus to 134 units, along with a diabetic diet and blood glucose monitoring.			
Infection Consultation Note: It is recommended to start Cezol 3*1 g, with reassessment after 3 days.			
Orthopedics Consultation Note: No signs of chronic osteomyelitis.			
Cardiovascular Surgery Consultation Note: Coraspirin 100 mg once daily, Trental CR 600 mg twice daily, wound dressing, and orthopedic consultation were recommended.			
Plastic Surgery Consultation Note: Debridement was recommended prior to amputation.			

Table 2. Clinical Patient Orders

NAME OF THE MEDICATION	DOSE	ROUTE	HOUR	HOUR	HOUR	HOUR
Coralan	2*5 mg	(PO)	06		18	
Lantus	1*34 U	(SC)				22
Apidra	3*10 U	(SC)	06	12	18	
Ator	1*40 mg	(PO)	08			
Problok	1*50 mg	(PO)	08			
Agrilor	2*90 mg	(PO)	06		18	
Coversyl	1*10 mg	(PO)	08			
Ecopirin	1*100 mg	(PO)				
Sulcid flk	3*1 gr	(IV)	08		16	24
Pantpas flk	1*1	(IV)	08			
izotonik 1000 cc	1*1	(IV)	08			

the region, was diagnosed. This disease poses a high transmission risk, especially with the deterioration of socioeconomic conditions and living standards.

Scabies treatment recommendations included

- **Armec 3 mg tablets:** 1 × 6 tablets as a single dose on an empty stomach.

- **Hygiene protocol:** If possible, take a bath and change clothes and bed linens two days after the medication.

Second dose: Take the second dose of the medication in the same manner after 10 days.

Isolation and sanitation measures:

- The patient was placed under contact isolation during their stay in the clinic.

Linens and other personal items belonging to the patient were to be placed in a separate bag (absorbable infectious waste bag) and sent to the laundry. The laundry staff was informed about handling these items appropriately.

Throughout the patient's stay in the clinic, local wound care was applied following the surgical debridement.

DISCUSSION

Diabetic foot ulcers clinically present as a cut in the epidermis, and most likely a portion of the dermis. Pre-ulcerative lesions are closed or superficial lesions confined to the epidermis (such as blisters, calluses, erythema, or warmth), but they are more likely to evolve into ulcers. Minor trauma often leads to the development of ulcers, which frequently occur due to increased pressure in weight-bearing areas of the plantar surface, abnormal gait, ill-fitting shoes, or unnoticed injury on an insensitive foot (e.g., ingrown toenails, puncture wounds, or burns), resulting from friction and shearing. Structural deformities, such as Charcot neuroarthropathy, increase the incidence of diabetic foot ulcers. These ulcers often occur due to a complex interaction of multiple factors following a moderately traumatic event. Diabetic foot ulcers, which account for more than 60% of all non-traumatic amputations, are a significant cause of morbidity and mortality. Infected or ischemic diabetic foot ulcers account for approximately 20% of all hospitalization days in diabetic patients. The main factors contributing to foot ulcers in diabetic patients are microvascular and macrovascular damage, neuropathy, and joint mobility restrictions, along with other factors such as excessive pressure, foot deformity, calluses, trauma, and infection.

The first step in the management of diabetic foot ulcers is to classify the ulcer. The Wagner classification system is the most commonly used method to grade the severity of ulcers, with scores ranging from 0 to 5. The Wagner classification system is shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Wagner Classification System

Grade	Description
0	No open lesions; may have pre-ulcerative lesions, healed ulcers, or presence of bony deformity.
1	Superficial ulcer involving the epidermis and dermis.
2	Deep ulcer extending to the subcutaneous tissue, but not involving bone or joint.
3	Deep ulcer with abscess or osteomyelitis.
4	Gangrene localized to the forefoot or heel.
5	Extensive gangrene involving the entire foot.

In the study by Bozkurt et al. (2011), which evaluated the Wagner classification and culture results in patients with diabetic foot infections, it was reported that when patients were classified according to the Wagner scale upon hospital admission, 12 patients were classified as stage 1,²⁶ as stage 2, 15 as stage 3, and 10 as stage 4.²⁸ In the study by Kayaş et al. (2018), which assessed the dermatological findings in diabetic foot syndrome, it was reported that according to the Wagner classification, 7.5% of patients had stage 1, 27.4% had stage 2, 28.6% had stage 3, 26.6% had stage 4, and 10% had stage 5 diabetic foot ulcers²⁹. In accordance with the literature, our patient's clinical etiology started with swelling under the right great toe, presenting as closed or superficial lesions limited to the epidermis, and according to the Wagner classification system, this is a stage 2 diabetic foot ulcer. The cause of this condition could be attributed to the patient's improper foot care and shoe choice, as well as the deterioration in living standards due to the region being an earthquake zone, the poor physical conditions of the environment where diabetic patients reside (such as living in containers or tents), and increased foreign body trauma in areas like fields and gardens, which contribute to the development of diabetic foot ulcers.

Diabetic patients have significantly weakened immune systems compared to healthy individuals. Therefore, the presence of infections in diabetic patients poses a serious and potentially fatal issue that can lead to limb loss¹². Previous research

findings indicate that wounds in patients with diabetic foot ulcers are frequently infected by various bacteria, including *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, and *P. aeruginosa*¹³. These bacteria penetrate deeper into the fascia through irritated or poorly perfused skin, leading to sepsis and life-threatening infections. Moreover, resistant bacterial strains such as methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) often infect diabetic foot ulcers, further increasing the risk of amputation^{14,15}.

In the study by Kayaş et al. (2018), which evaluated infections in diabetic foot ulcers, mild infection was observed in 27.8% of cases, moderate infection in 47.3%, and severe infection in 24.9%. Additionally, osteomyelitis was detected in the affected foot in 47.3% of patients at the time of admission²⁹. Consistent with the literature, a wound culture obtained from our patient during their hospital stay revealed the growth of *Enterococcus faecalis*. Antibiogram results showed susceptibility to ampicillin, and the patient was treated with Sulcid 3×1 grams. Throughout the patient's hospitalization, CRP and procalcitonin levels remained within normal ranges, and only mild signs of infection were observed in the wound.

Effective management and treatment protocols for diabetic foot ulcers should be initiated immediately after their onset. The gold standard for traditional diabetic foot ulcer treatments includes wound debridement, dressings, infection management, revascularization, drainage, hyperbaric oxygen therapy, and negative pressure vacuum therapy¹⁶. Wound debridement is the most fundamental approach for managing diabetic foot ulcers. It involves removing necrotic or contaminated tissue, blood clots, and unwanted debris from the wound bed. The most common forms of debridement are ultrasonic, biological, enzymatic, and surgical debridement^{17,18}. Furthermore, debridement accelerates the healing process by removing necrotic and infected tissue as well as bacterial biofilms¹⁶.

In alignment with the literature, when our patient first presented to the chronic wound care clinic, they were assessed with a multidisciplinary approach, and debridement was chosen as the primary treatment method. Initially, enzymatic debridement was preferred, and the patient received daily local wound care with W Cura D cream for two weeks. During this process, the wound was evaluated at each dressing change in terms of its size (length, width, and depth), exudate amount, color, consistency, and characteristics. The surrounding skin was assessed for appearance, color, temperature, and signs of infection.

As no improvement was observed in the wound, the patient was admitted to the wound care clinic for surgical debridement. Following preoperative preparation, surgical debridement was performed with an ASA III risk assessment. After debridement, antibiotic therapy was administered based on the wound culture antibiogram, along with local wound dressings. Complete healing of the patient's wound was achieved.

Wound dressings are a traditional wound care approach composed of natural, modified, or synthetic materials and medical components. An effective wound dressing should provide a moist environment that promotes tissue regeneration, keratinocyte migration, revascularization, granulation, and inhibits bacterial growth^{19,20}. In line with the literature, surgical debridement was performed on our patient to remove necrotic tissues. Local wound care products were sequentially applied to support tissue regeneration, keratinocyte migration, revascularization, and granulation. By maintaining an appropriate moist environment, the diabetic foot ulcer progressed through the stages of wound healing and completely healed within approximately 12 weeks.

Infection is frequently present during the healing process of wounds, particularly in diabetic patients. If more than two of the typical signs of inflammation (redness, warmth, edema, pain, and loss of function) are observed, the presence of infection is suspected. Aerobic Gram-positive cocci and staphylococci are the most commonly identified microorganisms responsible for the majority of diabetic foot ulcers. Narrow-spectrum antibiotics may be used for mild to moderate wound infections, while broad-spectrum parenteral antibiotics are recommended for severe wound infections^{21,22}.

In accordance with the literature, our patient, who had a mild wound infection, was treated with a narrow-spectrum antibiotic, Sulcid, at a dose of 3x1 grams for 10 days, as per the wound culture antibiogram. For home care following discharge, Augmentin 3x1 grams and Ciprofloxacin 2x500 mg were prescribed.

The literature emphasizes additional factors in managing diabetic foot ulcers, such as glycemic control, precise antibiotic use, vascular assessment, and psychotherapy^{23,24}. Poorly managed and irregular blood sugar levels negatively impact wound healing in diabetic foot ulcer patients, significantly prolonging the process. Even worse, amputation becomes inevitable in patients unable to achieve proper blood sugar regulation.

In alignment with the literature, upon the initial visit to our outpatient clinic, the patient's HbA1C level was 9.54%, and fasting blood sugar was 169 mg/dL. Following recommendations from the internal medicine specialist, insulin therapy was adjusted to Apidra 3x14 units (for blood sugar levels exceeding 200 mg/dL) and Lantus 1x34 units. Additionally, a diabetic diet and regular blood sugar monitoring were advised. The patient's blood sugar monitoring chart is presented in Table 4.

During the patient's hospitalization and post-discharge periods, glycemic control was achieved, leading to the complete healing of the diabetic foot ulcer.

If the condition progresses to a point where limb salvage is no longer an option, amputation becomes a life-saving alternative. Despite the availability of several treatment options, managing diabetic foot ulcers remains one of the most challenging diabetes-related complications.^{25,26} Although amputation is a life-saving alternative in patients with diabetic foot ulcers, it adversely affects quality of life and is a major cause of mortality and morbidity.

Table 4. Blood Sugar Monitoring Chart

Date	06:00		12:00		18:00		22:00	
	Insulin Dose	Bg	Insulin Dose	Bg	Insulin Dose	Bg	Insulin Dose	Bg
19/03/24	10 U	155	10 U	145	6 U	89	10 U	98
20/03/24	PREOP	143	POSTOP	97	14U	250	20U	120
21/03/24	10 U	156	10 U	182	10 U	123	34 U	187
22/03/24	10 U	155	10 U	194	10 U	136	34 U	204
23/03/24	10 U	148	10 U	104	10 U	170	20 U	104
24/03/24	14 U	260	10 U	98	10 U	169	34 U	265
25/03/24	10 U	109	10 U	180	14 U	239	34 U	215
26/03/24	10 U	122	----	78	14 U	213	34 U	200
27/03/24	10 U	156	10 U	136	10 U	143	34 U	195
28/03/24	10 U	139	----	76	10 U	196	34 U	166
29/03/24	10 U	115	10 U	155	10 U	148	34 U	154
30/03/24	10 U	163	10 U	177	10 U	186	34 U	178
31/03/24	10 U	89	10 U	142	10 U	139	34 U	185
01/04/24	10 U	159	10 U	132	The patient has been discharged.			

Therefore, the most effective treatment for diabetic foot ulcers in diabetic patients is to prevent their development and, if an ulcer has developed, to diagnose it at an early stage and provide appropriate care and treatment management.

In accordance with the literature, our patient's diabetic foot ulcer was classified as Stage 2 according to the Wagner classification system. The underlying diseases and pathologies were brought under control, glycemic regulation was achieved, and with surgical debridement and proper wound care management, the risk of amputation was eliminated. No additional complications occurred in the patient.

CONCLUSION

The complex etiology of diabetic wounds and the reduced

healing capacity in individuals with diabetes remain significant challenges for healthcare systems and medical professionals worldwide. Diabetic foot ulcers are a global concern, significantly increasing amputation rates worldwide. Reports indicate that approximately one amputation occurs every second, with 84% of these due to diabetic foot ulcers.²⁷ Managing chronic wounds is thus an intricate and demanding process.

The care and management of diabetic foot ulcers can be effectively achieved through a multidisciplinary team approach. The foundation of wound management lies in identifying the underlying cause, applying targeted treatment and care, addressing other risk factors present in the patient, and providing individualized care specific to each patient.

In this context, nurses play a critical role in managing diabetic foot ulcers. From the initial patient encounter, nurses should:

- Obtain a comprehensive medical history.
- Identify patient-specific risk factors.
- Conduct a thorough physical examination of the affected foot, evaluating its temperature, moisture, color, edema, and capillary refill time, and perform neurovascular assessments.

- Monitor circulation by assessing pulses.
- Examine the skin surrounding the ulcer.

Plan, implement, and evaluate interventions to identify and address pathogens causing the ulcer.

These actions form the cornerstone of effective care and are essential to improving outcomes in patients with diabetic foot ulcers.

Ethical Aspect

Verbal and written consent were obtained from the patient for the case presentation.

Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest is reported by the authors.

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